

Enhancing cybersecurity in railways: Machine learning approaches for attack detection

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ABSTRACT

Ensuring the security of railway systems is crucial to protecting both passengers and infrastructure from the increasing threat of cyberattacks. As these threats grow in complexity and frequency, the need for resilient attack detection systems becomes more pressing.

This study tackles the challenge of attack detection in railway systems using machine learning techniques. By integrating Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and Transfer Learning (TL), we enhance detection accuracy and develop a robust approach capable of identifying both known and emerging threats. Our methodology utilized the Electra Modbus dataset as the source domain and was transferred to the Electra S7Comm dataset as the target domain. Experimental results highlight the effectiveness of GAN-based data augmentation in mitigating the scarcity of attack samples, enhancing both the robustness and generalizability of our detection models. Additionally, the application of pre-trained models through transfer learning played a crucial role in achieving superior performance. Our proposed solution can be deployed within railway networks to strengthen security measures, enabling proactive responses to cyber threats, safeguarding critical infrastructure, and ensuring uninterrupted operations.

1. Introduction

As society and industry undergo continuous digitalization, the looming threat of cyber-attacks is steadily increasing Gabriel et al. [1]. Even critical infrastructures, such as railway companies, are not immune to these malicious threats. The critical assets in railway infrastructures that are exposed to cyber threats include control systems, communication networks, signaling systems, ticketing systems, passenger information, etc. A cyberattack targeting any of these critical assets can pose serious risks, as service disruptions or collisions. Recent cyberattacks include ransomware attacks in the UK affecting the rail signaling system that caused the delay and cancellation of rail services, or in Spain exposing gigabytes of personal and business data.

Therefore, ensuring the security and safety of railway systems is of utmost importance to protect both passengers and infrastructure. Given the increasing complexity and frequency of cyberattacks, it is imperative to have robust mechanisms for detecting such attacks. This requires not only identifying existing attacks but also uncovering potential unknown threats.

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence techniques have enabled the detection of cyberattacks across diverse domains [2,3]. This presents an opportunity to leverage these techniques for the detection

of cyber threats within railway systems. The framework proposed in this paper is motivated by the increasing role of artificial intelligence in cyberattack detection and its potential to enhance the security of railway infrastructures. The main aim of this initiative is to address the complex issue of identifying and categorizing cyberattacks in a railway scenario, using advanced machine learning techniques (ML).

The simulation of the railway scenario involves considering a dataset, which includes network traffic data from an electric traction station operating under normal conditions, as well as data collected during cyberattacks. It is important to note that the samples associated with each event type, encompassing both network traffic and cyberattacks, exhibit an inherent imbalance. Specifically, the dataset has a reduced number of cyberattacks instances, which requires augmenting these less prevalent samples. Balancing the dataset enhances results without inducing overfitting of the model, aligning the class distribution. The aim is to optimize the ratio between different represented classes or categories in the dataset by addressing the imbalance, as outlined in [4].

To address the data imbalance, we used the oversampling technique, which involves increasing the number of samples for categories that

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are underrepresented in the dataset. We accomplished this by utilizing Generative Models, which are well-suited for generating new samples. Specifically, we found that Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) were the best choice for data expansion in our model, as they represent an advanced form of Generative Modeling. This selection is underscored by the recognition that data augmentation is a simplified variant of Generative Modeling, affirming the appropriateness of GANs for the task at hand, as discussed in [5].

After detecting and categorizing the attacks, it is imperative to integrate Transfer Learning (TL) for identifying and classifying zero-day attacks. TL is a contemporary breakthrough in machine learning that leverages previously acquired knowledge from a related source domain to enhance performance in a target domain. TL establishes a high-performance learner tailored for the target domain by capitalizing on insights gained from the related source domain. The transfer of knowledge from one domain to another has been proven to yield superior results compared to training a model entirely from scratch using the new dataset.

Research suggests that TL models perform similarly to deep learning (DL) models, even when TL is applied with a small percentage of labeled training data (usually between one and ten percent). This approach shows promising results in detecting new intrusions with greater accuracy. Previous research has used TL to improve the identification of known cyberattacks in datasets with limited samples, thereby accelerating the training process, as noted in [6]. Other studies have focused on detecting emerging families of attacks [7] or specific IoT applications, such as the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) [8].

This study presents a robust framework for detecting and classifying novel attacks in railway scenarios, using TL. The objective is to develop an efficient intrusion detection framework that can function seamlessly within systems with limited computing capacity. In conclusion, the main contributions of this article are the following:

1. Implementation of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for detecting and categorizing cyberattacks in railway systems, involving several stages, from data collection to model deployment.
2. Design and implementation of the GAN-based augmentation technique to achieve a balanced dataset. This requires the identification of the proper GAN architecture tailored to suit the unique characteristics of the dataset.
3. Evaluation of the framework for detecting cyberattacks in railway systems through a comparative analysis of the accuracy and successful detection of zero-day attacks considering TL technique.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews existing solutions for the Electra dataset using artificial intelligence. Section 3 provides an overview of key concepts necessary to understand the attack detection approach used in this study. Section 4 introduces the proposed cybersecurity framework for railway infrastructure. Section 5 outlines the novel TL framework for attack detection and classification. Section 6 describes the experiments conducted and discusses the results obtained. Section 7 discusses the ethical risks and mitigation strategies in applying AI systems to railway systems. Finally, Section 9 summarizes the findings and concludes the study.

2. Related work

Due to the increasing importance of detecting cyberattacks, several studies have emerged in recent years that use artificial intelligence for attack detection. The Electra dataset has played a crucial role in advancing progress in this field in the railways critical infrastructure.

Initially, investigations using the Electra dataset focused solely on attack detection without delving into their classification. Some studies relied on a single protocol [9–13]. Li Yanjie et al. (2020) proposed a detection algorithm based on TrAdaBoost, a TL algorithm, combined with

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [12]. Their findings demonstrated a decrease in the error rate with the application of transfer learning.

Later investigations using the Electra dataset extended their scope beyond attack detection, addressing also the classification of identified attacks. Subsequent studies either adopted a single protocol [14] or employed two protocols [15–17]. However, none of these studies conduct a comprehensive analysis that covers both protocols, fine-tunes the model for detecting and classifying attacks within the source domain, and ultimately establishes a framework for detecting and classifying new attacks through TL. This work combines the insights from each of the related works mentioned above.

Table 1 provides a chronological overview of relevant papers, including the authors' names, publication year, methodology, and evaluation metrics. The techniques used range from Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), One-Class Support Vector Machines (OCSVM), Isolation Forest (IF), Deep Neural Networks (DNN), CNN, to GAN. Dimensionality Reduction Techniques (DAE), Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE), T-Link, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), LSTM, and neural networks with an augmented hidden layer (NAHL) were used in the Electra Modbus context. The evaluation metrics, including accuracy (ACC), precision, recall, and F1-score, were used to comprehensively assess the models' performance.

This work is based on Li Yanjie et al.'s (2020) demonstration of the effectiveness of TL in the Electra dataset. The proposed framework combines TL within a CNN framework and incorporates GAN data augmentation. This approach is effective in detecting and classifying attacks, as well as uncovering previously unidentified attack types. The detection of new attacks adds a new dimension to the use of the Electra dataset, which has not been explored previously.

3. Background

In this section, we outline the stages involved in developing a Neural Network (NN). We also examine the characteristics of CNNs and GANs, emphasizing their key attributes, as these networks are central to our work. In addition, we explore the functionality and benefits of transfer learning. Finally, we conclude the section by describing the metrics used to evaluate the proposed framework.

3.1. Stages of neural network development

The creation of a neural network involves several distinct stages, each of which plays a crucial role in building an efficient and reliable model. These stages can be summarized as follows: data preprocessing, training, and validation/testing. During data preprocessing, the input data is processed and prepared for the network. Data cleaning techniques are used to deal with missing values, outliers, or inconsistent data. Furthermore, to ensure comparable scales for all features, data transformation methods such as scaling or normalization can be employed. Additionally, categorical variables can be encoded into numerical representations using techniques like label encoding, which replaces each category with a corresponding integer value. This allows compatibility with the network architecture. Additionally, categorical variables can be encoded into numerical representations using techniques like label encoding, which replaces each category with a corresponding integer value. During the training phase, the network learns from preprocessed data to adjust its internal parameters. The data is divided into batches, and the network goes through a number of iterations, known as epochs. At each epoch, the network processes data through its layers, computes an output, and compares it to the expected output using a defined loss function. The network then adjusts its weights and biases through backpropagation to minimize loss and improve performance. The training phase continues until a predetermined stopping criterion is met, such as reaching a maximum number of epochs or achieving satisfactory performance. During the validation and testing phase, a portion of the data is used to validate the

Table 1
Security approaches using different models for attack detection in Electra dataset.

Reference works	Model	% ACC/Precision/Recall/F1-score
Perales Gómez et al. [9]	RF	-/98.77/98.71/98.74
	SVM	-/97.56/100/98.76
Perales Gómez et al. [11]	OCSVM	-/96.92/100/98.43
	IF	-/98.62/98.56/98.59
	DNN	-/87.39/100/93.27
Ning et al. [10]	GAN and DNN	-/-/0.98/-
Li et al. [12]	LSTM	Error rate compared to LSTM alone
Conti et al. [13]	RF	-/98.8/-/98.7
Jiang and Lin [14]	DNN	-/99.0/99.0/99.0
Jiang and Chen [15]	DAE, SMOTE, T-Link, XGBoost	-/99.68/97.67/98.50
Vasilyev et al. [16]	RF with XGBClassifier	97.5/-/-/96.4
Berghout and Benbouzid [17]	NAHL	99.79/99.0/99.81/99.39
	CNN	93.52/93.17/92.65/92.22

Fig. 1. CNN architecture.

results and evaluate the network's performance. The hyperparameters of the CNN are modified using error gradients to increase accuracy. The validation process is monitored to learn in real-time during each iteration. Additionally, various hyperparameters, such as the learning rate, number of hidden layers, or activation functions, are adjusted to strike a balance between underfitting and overfitting. Finally, testing with performance matrices enables the determination of whether the process has been carried out correctly. It is important to note that the dataset used for this phase should be independent of the one used in both the training and validation phases.

3.2. CNNs

CNNs are a popular type of DNN. They have achieved remarkable results in image and natural language processing Ramprasath et al. [18], Pandey and Wang [19] and Li et al. [20]. CNNs are also being applied in the cybersecurity field for intrusion detection and encrypted traffic classification [21–23]. The architecture of a CNN (refer to Fig. 1) comprises three types of layers: convolutional, pooling, and classification. Convolutional layers are the fundamental building blocks of a CNN. They consist of units that are arranged in feature maps. Each unit in a feature map is connected to local patches in the feature maps of the previous layer through a set of weights known as a filter bank. The output of these filters undergoes a non-linear transformation. Pooling layers merge similar features using a specific function, reducing the size of feature maps and the number of overfitting parameters. The final step involves the use of classifiers, which are made up of fully connected layers, to classify the detected features.

3.3. GANs

A GAN is a deep learning model that learns patterns from data and generates new samples resembling the original ones [24]. Its primary purpose is to produce synthetic data that mirrors the characteristics of real data within a dataset, particularly aiming to augment the representation of underrepresented classes.

Fig. 2 illustrates the fundamental architecture of a GAN. The generative model creates a new sample by extracting latent features from the original data distribution and adding noise data to it. The input of the discriminative model is either a sample data or a recently generated sample. The discriminator classifies the sample as either real or fake, penalizing the generator in the former case. Therefore, the training process is essentially a feedback loop between the two adversarial networks. The generator produces higher-quality and credible samples, while the discriminator becomes better at identifying real data from artificial samples. In this work, GAN models have been used to balance intrusion datasets by generating new instances of the underrepresented attack class. The augmented dataset is richer and more suitable for training an attack classifier than the original dataset.

To determine the adequacy of the results, it is essential to analyze the losses in both the generator (L_G) and discriminator (L_D) of the GAN. Eq. (1) shows how to calculate these losses.

$$L_G = -\log D(G(z)); L_D = -\log D(x) - \log(1 - D(G(z))) \quad (1)$$

The generated data from the generator is represented by $G(z)$, where z is the random noise vector. The discriminator is denoted by D and x represents real data from the training set.

The aim is to achieve a balance in the losses of both the generator and the discriminator. A high generator loss indicates that the generated data does not closely resemble the actual data, whereas a high discriminator loss suggests that the discriminator struggles to differentiate between real and generated data. This objective is typically formulated as a two-player *minimax* optimization problem, as illustrated by Eq. (2).

$$\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = \mathbb{E}_x[\log D(x)] + \mathbb{E}_z[\log(1 - D(G(z)))] \quad (2)$$

where \mathbb{E} denotes the expectation.

The performance of the GAN function is significantly influenced by three critical parameters: *nbatch*, *niterations*, and *nsample*. *Nbatch* denotes the batch size used in GAN training. A batch comprises the data group processed in each iteration to update the network weights. While

Fig. 2. GAN architecture.

a larger batch size can enhance velocity, it may demand more computer memory. $N_{iterations}$ represents the number of iterations completed during GAN training. Each iteration involves processing a batch of data and updating network weights by calculating the loss function. Finally, n_{sample} indicates the number of samples generated by the GAN after each iteration. These samples constitute new data generated by the GAN to mimic the original training data. The generator takes a noise vector as input and processes it to produce an output that resembles the actual data. Choosing appropriate values for n_{batch} , $n_{iterations}$, and n_{sample} is essential for enabling the GAN to capture the inherent patterns in the real data. This guarantees that the generated samples are of high quality, diverse, and accurately represent the distribution of the real data. To generate the desired number of data samples, $n_{generated}$, these parameters must adhere to Eq. (3).

$$n_{generated} = \frac{n_{iterations} \cdot n_{batch}}{n_{samples}} \quad (3)$$

3.4. TL model

TL is necessary for the detection and classification of novel attacks as it allows models to benefit from pre-existing knowledge rather than starting the learning process from scratch [25]. By capturing the underlying structure and patterns of the data, the model can generalize its knowledge and effectively identify new attacks that have similar patterns. To apply TL, a source domain set and a target set must be established. The domain set is a large dataset in a similar field to the target set. It serves as the foundation for training the model.

The process of transfer learning typically involves two stages: pre-training and fine-tuning [26]. In the pretraining stage, a model is trained on a large dataset to learn general representations and patterns from the data. This pretrained model captures high-level features and knowledge that can be valuable for various tasks.

In the fine-tuning stage, the pretrained model is further trained on a smaller labeled dataset specific to the target task. During this stage, certain layers or blocks of the pre-trained model are frozen, which means that their parameters are kept fixed and not updated during training. By adapting the pre-trained knowledge to the new task, the model refines its representations and learns to make task-specific predictions.

3.5. Performance metrics

This section defines the metrics used in this study to assess the performance of the developed framework.

3.5.1. Confusion matrix

A confusion matrix is a useful tool for visualizing the performance of supervised learning algorithms, such as CNNs [27]. Fig. 3 shows a graphical representation of the confusion matrix. Each column represents the number of predictions for a specific class, while each row represents instances of the actual class. True positives (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), and false negatives (FN) are defined.

		Predicted Class	
		Normal	Attack
Actual Class	Normal	TN: Correctly identified as attack.	FP: Incorrectly labeled as normal.
	Attack	FN: Incorrectly labeled as attack.	TP: Correctly identified as normal.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix scheme for binary classification [28].

3.5.2. Accuracy (ACC) metric

ACC represents the proportion of correctly classified predictions relative to the total number of evaluated instances. It is a widely used and fundamental prediction metric for CNNs, providing a practical assessment of neural network performance. The ACC can be calculated using Eq. (4):

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (4)$$

3.5.3. Recall metric

Recall (also known as sensitivity or true positive rate) measures the model's ability to correctly identify instances of a given class. The recall metric per each class i can be calculated using Eq. (5):

$$Recall_i = \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i} \quad (5)$$

3.5.4. Precision metric

In a multiclass classification scenario, Precision for each class measures the accuracy of the model when predicting an instance as belonging to that specific class. It calculates the proportion of TP predictions for a class relative to all instances predicted as belonging to that class, including both TP and FP. The formula for Precision for class i is given in Eq. (6).

$$Precision_i = \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} \quad (6)$$

3.5.5. F1-score metric

The F1-score metric in a multiclass confusion matrix is calculated individually for each class. It is based on the relationship between precision and recall for each class. The F1-score metric per each class i can be calculated using Eq. (7):

$$F1 - score_i = \frac{2 * Precision_i * Recall_i}{Precision_i + Recall_i} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 4. Railway framework.

3.5.6. False negative rate

The False Negative Rate (FNR) is a metric used to assess a model's performance, especially in classification tasks. It measures the proportion of actual positive instances that are incorrectly classified as negative by the model. A lower FNR indicates better performance in identifying positive instances. The FNR for each class i can be calculated using Eq. (8):

$$FNR_i = \frac{FN_i}{TP_i + FN_i} \quad (8)$$

4. Detection, recommendation and response framework in the railway infrastructure

This section introduces the proposed cybersecurity framework designed to protect railway systems from evolving cyber threats. The framework builds upon the PHOENIX Framework [29], adapting its principles specifically to railway environments while emphasizing the detection and mitigation phases. The PHOENIX framework is a comprehensive Cyber Resilience Framework, which leverages Artificial Intelligence (AI)-assisted orchestration, automation, and response mechanisms to ensure business continuity and efficient incident response. By incorporating these capabilities, PHOENIX enables proactive threat management and resilience against cyber incidents. It is tailored to Operators of Essential Services (OES) and EU Member State National Authorities. The proposed railway framework, as illustrated in Fig. 4, consists of two main modules: the Attack Prediction Response recommendation and adaptation (APR) and the Resilience Orchestration, Automation, and Response (ROAR). The APR module is responsible for pre-processing data collected from the railway infrastructure, extracting relevant features, and generating structured datasets (e.g., CSV files). The processed data serves as input for AI-driven models, which are trained to detect cyberattacks with high accuracy. Upon identifying an attack, the APR module generates a response strategy, outlining the necessary preventive and mitigation actions tailored to the specific threat. The ROAR module plays a crucial role in executing mitigation strategies within the railway infrastructure. It defines Resilience Playbooks (RPs), which are structured action plans specifying predefined mitigation steps in response to detected threats. These playbooks are orchestrated and deployed in real time, ensuring a swift and coordinated response to cyber incidents. Additionally, ROAR continuously monitors the execution of mitigation actions, tracks their progress, and collects evidence generated throughout the process. This feedback loop enables the refinement of future response strategies. By integrating these components, the proposed framework enhances the cyber resilience of railway systems, enabling early threat detection and automated incident response while minimizing disruptions to critical railway operations.

To illustrate the operational flow of the proposed framework, we present a hypothetical use case involving a Read Data attack. In this scenario, an unauthorized entity gains access to communication or configuration data within the railway's digital infrastructure.

Threat detection is conducted through strategically deployed Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), which monitor network traffic at

critical points such as interlockings, SCADA systems, train control networks, and signaling systems. These sensors employ protocols such as Modbus to capture and analyze data packets, identifying anomalous read requests. Captured traffic is processed by the Data Collection and Preprocessing Data modules outlined in Fig. 4. Subsequently, the CNN-TL model analyzes the data and classifies the threat as a Read Data attack. Following threat identification, the framework queries a database of known attack signatures to recommend tailored mitigation strategies. It further assesses whether the network has been compromised and distinguishes between espionage and sabotage techniques, enabling the isolation of affected network segments. All response actions are orchestrated by the Automation and Response module, which initiates immediate system containment, restores secure configurations from backup copies, updates firmware on routers and firewalls, and implements additional measures to eradicate the threat and ensure full operational recovery.

The following sections present the TL-based attack detection framework implemented within the APR module. A particular focus is given to the application of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Transfer Learning (TL) techniques, which improve threat detection capabilities in railway infrastructures. These AI-driven enhancements contribute to more robust and adaptive cybersecurity measures, ensuring greater protection against sophisticated cyber threats.

5. TL-based attack detection framework

The TL-based attack detection framework consists of four main stages, as illustrated in Fig. 5. This section outlines the key elements of each stage: the datasets used, data preprocessing, the optimal CNN model, the characteristics of the GAN for data balancing and augmenting underrepresented classes, and the CNN-TL model employed.

5.1. Datasets: *Electra modbus* and *electra S7Comm*

The *Electra* dataset [30] was generated from the network traffic of an electrical traction substation operating in both normal and attacked modes. This dataset was meticulously curated within a realistic environment, incorporating industrial-grade devices such as Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) and a SCADA system. The communication protocols used in the dataset include well-established industrial protocols such as Modbus and S7Comm, making it a valuable resource for studying security in industrial control systems (ICS).

The *Electra Modbus* and *Electra S7Comm* datasets represent distinct domains within ICS, which justifies the need for a comparative analysis. This comparison is essential for understanding the model's performance and effectiveness across different operational contexts, which is a crucial factor when applying detection methods in real-world industrial environments.

The Modbus protocol is one of the most widely used protocols in industrial automation, with origins dating back to the late 1970s [31]. Known for its simplicity, openness, and platform independence, Modbus is widely adopted to connect a diverse range of devices and systems

Fig. 5. Attack detection framework stages.

across various industrial environments. Its master–slave architecture facilitates communication, making it an ideal choice for heterogeneous setups where compatibility between different devices is key. The simplicity of Modbus leads to relatively straightforward network traffic patterns, making it easier to monitor and analyze. However, this simplicity also means that attackers can exploit vulnerabilities in a broad range of devices and systems. The attacks recorded in the Electra Modbus dataset include Denial-of-Service (DoS), replay attacks, and fuzzing, which are generic attack types commonly associated with this protocol.

On the other hand, S7Comm, or Siemens S7 Communication, is a proprietary protocol developed specifically for Siemens PLCs and automation systems. It is widely used in industrial sectors where Siemens equipment dominates, such as in manufacturing and process control environments. The S7Comm protocol is more complex and tailored to Siemens systems, and its architecture allows for more specialized communication patterns. This results in more intricate network traffic compared to Modbus. Consequently, the Electra S7Comm dataset includes targeted attacks that exploit the specific vulnerabilities in Siemens PLCs, such as unauthorized data block manipulation, execution of illegitimate commands, and manipulation of communication sessions. These types of attacks are unique to environments where Siemens devices are employed and require a more nuanced approach for detection and mitigation.

The comparison between Electra Modbus and Electra S7Comm datasets is critical, as they belong to different ICS protocol domains. This distinction enhances the understanding of how detection methods perform in varied industrial contexts. The Modbus dataset tests detection models in a more heterogeneous, multi-vendor environment, while the S7Comm dataset focuses on a vendor-specific environment, where the detection needs are more specialized due to the proprietary nature of the communication. Thus, analyzing both datasets provides a more comprehensive view of the detection approach’s generalizability and effectiveness across different ICS configurations. Table 2 summarizes the key differences between the Electra Modbus and Electra S7Comm datasets.

The common features present in both datasets, such as the packet structure, traffic patterns, and specific attack types, are summarized in the following Table 3. This comparative analysis aids in better understanding the strengths and limitations of detection methods applied to Modbus-based and Siemens-specific ICS environments.

Tables 4 and 5 display the distribution of attacks and benign traffic for the Electra Modbus and Electra S7Comm protocols, respectively. The distribution between normal traffic and attacks is significantly different between the two datasets. For Electra Modbus, the split is 94.8% normal traffic versus 5.2% attacks, while for Electra S7Comm,

Table 2
Comparison between Electra Modbus and Electra S7Comm datasets.

Feature	Electra Modbus	Electra S7Comm
Protocol	Modbus	S7Comm (Siemens proprietary)
Device type	General industrial devices	Siemens SIMATIC PLCs
Protocol architecture	Simple (Master–Slave)	Complex (Client–Server with proprietary ops)
Attack types	Generic (DoS, Replay, Fuzzing)	Specific (Data block manipulation, illegal commands)
Use case	General industrial networks	Siemens-specific environments
Model evaluation role	Tests generalizability	Tests protocol-specific performance

Table 3
Features, descriptions, and types of data in the Electra dataset.

Features	Descriptions	Types
time	Timestamp	string
smac	Source MAC address	string
dmac	Destination MAC address	string
sip	Source IP address	string
dip	Destination IP address	string
request	Indicating whether the packet is a request from the master to the slave	boolean
fc	Function code	integer
error	Indicating whether errors exist in read/writing operations	boolean
madd	Memory address for performing read/write operation	integer
data	Data for performing read/write operation	integer
label	Indicating either normality or the class of the attack	string

the ratio is more skewed toward normal traffic, with 98.58% normal and only 1.42% attacks. These distributions highlight the difference in the frequency and nature of attacks present in the datasets, with Electra S7Comm exhibiting a more benign traffic pattern overall.

Furthermore, the attack categories differ slightly between the two protocols. In the Electra Modbus dataset, attack types include Forced Error and Replay attacks, which exploit weaknesses in the Modbus

Table 4
Class categories of Electra Modbus dataset.

Category	Name	Size	Proportion # of samples
Normal	Normal	15 444 940	94.800%
	Read data	785 961	4.830%
	Function codes recognition	30 580	0.190%
Attack	Response modification	16 353	0.100%
	Write data	9 417	0.060%
	Forced error in response	1 129	0.007%
	Replay valid packets	897	0.006%

Table 5
Class categories of Electra S7Comm dataset.

Category	Name	Size	Proportion # of samples
Normal	Normal	292 806 268	98.580%
	Read data	936 306	0.320%
	Function codes recognition	265 757	0.090%
Attack	Response modification	144 892	0.050%
	Write data	2 235 772	0.760%
	Command modification	575 122	0.200%

Table 6
Label encoding for class categories from Electra Modbus and Electra S7Comm.

Class category	Code	
	Electra Modbus	Electra S7Comm
Forced error in response	0	–
Normal	1	1
Read data	2	2
Function codes recognition	3	3
Replay valid packets	4	–
Response modification	5	4
Write data	6	5
Command modification	–	0

protocol's simplicity. However, these categories are not present in the Electra S7Comm dataset. Instead, a new category, referred to as Command Attack, has been introduced. This category reflects the more complex and specialized nature of attacks targeting Siemens PLCs, where the focus is on exploiting command-based vulnerabilities within the S7Comm protocol. The shift in attack types underscores the differences in vulnerability profiles between the Modbus and Siemens-specific environments, further emphasizing the need for tailored detection methods in each case.

5.2. Data treatment and preprocessing

The data treatment and preprocessing procedure are applied to both the Electra Modbus and Electra S7Comm datasets. The appropriate treatment of network traffic allows CNN model efficiently predict non biased results, while a correct preprocessing avoid overfitting problems. Data structure is studied before starting the preprocessing. Both protocols of the Electra dataset are unbalanced since the number of records is far higher for normal traffic than for attacks.

The dataset undergoes refinement by excluding irrelevant features such as smac and dmac, and converting string-based attributes like sip and dip into integers. Unlabeled rows are discarded as they provide no useful information. Additionally, all data is normalized to achieve a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1, ensuring stability. As part of the dataset preparation for further analysis, identifying and removing null or missing values is crucial. Furthermore, label encoding is a key step that converts categorical labels into numerical values, enhancing the CNN's ability to process and learn from the data. This transformation assigns specific numeric codes to normal and attack categories for each Electra protocol, as detailed in Table 6.

Table 7
Neural network architecture.

Layer (type)	Output shape	Parameter #
convolution_1	(None, 7, 64)	448
batch_normalization_1	(None, 7, 64)	256
max_pooling1d_1	(None, 4, 64)	0
convolution_2	(None, 4, 64)	24,640
batch_normalization_2	(None, 4, 64)	256
max_pooling1d_2	(None, 2, 64)	0
convolution_3	(None, 2, 64)	24,640
batch_normalization_3	(None, 2, 64)	256
max_pooling1d_3	(None, 1, 64)	0
flatten	(None, 64)	0
dense_1	(None, 64)	4160
dense_2	(None, 64)	4160
dense_3	(None, 7)	455
Total parameters		59,271
Trainable parameters		58,887
Non-trainable parameters		384

Fig. 6. Scheme of the GAN's architecture.

5.3. DL model training and testing

The CNN architecture used involves the repetition of three key layers: a 1D Convolution layer with a *ReLU* activation function, followed by batch normalization to standardize the activations of the preceding layer, and a 1D *max pooling* layer to reduce the input length. The CNN architecture is designed to extract abstract and higher-level features from input data in a progressive manner (refer to Fig. 1). This design is based on a previous study [32] conducted on a different dataset that also employed TL techniques to identify new attacks, similar to our own study. The sequence of feature extraction layers is followed by a flatten layer that converts the multidimensional feature maps into a singular vector. Three dense layers are then incorporated to further process and refine the extracted features. The final dense layer comprises seven neurons, aligning with the desired output classes. Each neuron in this layer corresponds to one of the distinct output classes, allowing the network to generate predictions and classify input data effectively. Table 7 provides a detailed analysis of the trainable parameters.

5.4. Data augmentation using GAN

As mentioned in Section 3.3, the GAN is used to balance intrusion datasets by generating additional samples for the underrepresented attack class. Fig. 6 depicts the topology of the GAN used, illustrating the schema. The layers of both the generator and discriminator networks are delineated and arranged sequentially. The selection of each layer was based on multiple experimental trials.

Additionally, the *Adam* optimizer was selected for the compilation of the GAN, incorporating two key parameters: the learning rate and the beta parameter. The learning rate controls the speed at which

Table 8

GAN hyperparameters.

Hyperparameter	Value
LeakyReLU (α)	0.2
Optimizer learning rate (lr)	0.0002
Optimizer β	0.5
Loss function	Binary cross-entropy

Table 9

Parameter optimization for GAN in Electra Modbus.

Class category	niteration	nsample	nbatch
Function codes recognition	589	10	2000
Response modification	785	10	1500
Write data	785	10	1500
Forced error in response	884	3	400
Replay valid packets	1964	10	500

the neural network’s weights are adjusted during each iteration, while the beta parameter contributes to moment calculations, which are essential to the optimization process. Table 8 provides a comprehensive overview of the tested hyperparameters.

The overarching objective is to strike a balance in which the generator generates realistic samples capable of deceiving the discriminator, while the discriminator becomes increasingly adept at distinguishing between genuine and generated samples. To optimize this outcome, it is desirable to achieve loss values near 50%, indicating that the discriminator correctly identifies generated data roughly half of the time. To this end, numerous tests have been conducted with varying values of *nbatch*, *nsample*, and *niterations*. The resulting findings for these parameters are summarized in Table 9.

Table 9 highlights a notable aspect: the trend of decreasing values for *nbatch* in the least represented attacks. This observation is logical because the generation of synthetic data relies on processing an appropriate amount of data per iteration, which depends on the available data before augmentation. When a large volume of data is accessible, it is easier to generate a substantial amount in each iteration, ensuring balanced training. However, attempting to generate a significant amount of synthetic data from a relatively small sample, such as creating 10,000 data points from only 1000, can introduce instability and result in poorly generated data. Furthermore, it is important to consider why the value of *niterations* for the Replay attack is exceptionally high. This is mainly due to the Replay attack being a minority class within our dataset, consisting of only 897 instances. Expanding the dataset to 785,961, by increasing it in proportion to the largest observed attack, may introduce considerable instability, as this value significantly surpasses the original magnitude. Therefore, to generate data efficiently, it is essential to optimize the parameters of the GAN method meticulously. To visually track the trends depicted in Table 9 throughout the training process, refer to Figs. 7–11, illustrating the evolution of loss values for each of the augmented attacks. It is crucial to emphasize the paramount consideration given to data stabilization. Achieving a probability of precisely 50% is exceedingly challenging, thus our focus has been on attaining values proximate to this threshold while simultaneously ensuring a state of equilibrium where variations are substantially minimized.

5.5. CNN-TL model

This section provides an overview of the transfer learning (TL) procedure and its outcomes, with a specific focus on the transfer from Electra S7Comm to Electra Modbus. We begin by utilizing the pre-trained model described in Section 6.3. Next, we adapt this pre-trained model to the new dataset (Electra S7Comm).

In the early stages of the TL process, the layers of the pre-trained model are typically frozen, meaning their weights remain unchanged

Fig. 7. GAN losses for function codes recognition attack in Electra Modbus.

Fig. 8. GAN losses for response modification attack in Electra Modbus.

Fig. 9. GAN losses for Write Data attack in Electra Modbus.

Fig. 10. GAN losses for forced error in response attack in Electra Modbus.

when the new dataset is introduced. This strategy helps preserve the knowledge and features learned from the Electra Modbus dataset. After obtaining the adapted model, we proceed to train it with the target domain dataset. During this phase, the frozen layers retain their original weights from the pre-trained model (CNN-Base). Thus, transfer

Fig. 11. GAN losses for replay and packets attack in Electra Modbus.

learning involves adjusting the pretrained model to the new dataset while leveraging the previously acquired knowledge from the Electra Modbus dataset. Details of this process are provided in Section 6.4, where an overview of the CNN-TL framework is also presented.

6. Experiments and results

This section describes the experiments conducted to establish the framework. To achieve this goal, three distinct application scenarios were considered, designated as Method 1, 2, and 3. Fig. 12 shows schematic representations of these three methods.

The first approach involves balancing the distribution of data between benign and malignant attacks, without balancing the different categories of attacks, resulting in an uneven distribution of samples among the different types of attacks. This scenario uses the Electra Modbus dataset. Additionally, there is no need to artificially generate new samples using GANs in this case.

In contrast, the second method uses the same dataset as the previous approach but aims to balance the benign samples with the different categories of attacks considered, ensuring a fair representation of all attack types. To achieve this, new samples are synthesized for the underrepresented attacks using the parameterized GAN topology shown in Fig. 6.

Finally, the third method introduces the detection of new attacks that have not been covered in any of the previous scenarios, using TL. This scenario uses the Electra Modbus dataset. To correct the attacks' imbalance that lack sufficient representation, new samples are generated using a GAN to balance the distribution, similar to the second scenario.

The main goal of this evaluation is to determine whether the accuracy of attack detection and classification is improved by implementing data augmentation techniques and TL.

Next, we present the experiments conducted for each method, beginning with a description of the computational environment in which they were carried out.

Fig. 12. Overview of considered methods.

6.1. Development environment

The main experiments were conducted on an ASUS UX430U Notebook PC, powered by an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8550U CPU running at 1.80 GHz (with a boost to 1.99 GHz) and equipped with 16 GB of RAM. For the simulations, the environment utilized Python 3 (version 3.10.12), with key libraries including TensorFlow v2.11.0 [33], leveraging Keras from TensorFlow, as well as scikit-learn v1.5.2 [34], Pandas v2.2.3 [35], and Numpy v1.25.2 [36].

6.2. Method 1: Addressing class imbalance in attack categories

The first test analyzed the dataset directly using CNN (described in Section 5.3) without augmenting the data for the less represented attacks. However, due to a significant imbalance between the *Normal* and *Attack* categories, less accurate results were expected. The *Normal* data comprises 15,444,940 instances, much more represented than the combined total of *Attack* data, which consists of 844,337 instances. To reduce overfitting, we decreased the amount of *Normal* data to match the total amount of *Attack* data available in the dataset [37]. After training the model with the preprocessed data, as outlined in Section 5.2, we achieved an accuracy of 0.9851. The resulting confusion matrix for this case is shown in Fig. 13.

The accuracy obtained close to 1 is surprising, given the imbalance in the previous data. If high accuracy alone indicated correct detection, it would suggest successful optimization and effective attack discrimination by our CNN. However, the accuracy metric is not representative in an unbalanced dataset.

The high accuracy value is mainly due to the large number of correctly detected *Normal* instances. However, this dominance of *Normal* instances may create the impression that all attacks are being accurately detected, which is not the case. Despite the high overall accuracy, minority attacks may not be adequately captured and classified. This phenomenon can be illustrated through the following example. Suppose that there are 1000 data instances classified as *normal*, of which 900 is correctly detected. In contrast, there are 100 instances classified as *Attack*, but only 10 of them are detected accurately. In total, 910 out of 1100 instances are detected, resulting in an overall precision of 82.72%. However, the primary concern is accurately detecting the *Attack* data, which constitute only 10% of the total instances and is significantly lower than the initial estimate. It is important to balance the dataset by ensuring equal representation of both the *Normal* and *Attack* classes to obtain reliable and meaningful detection results.

To support the previous analysis, Table 10 provides additional metrics for each class. It shows that normal traffic (class 1) and read data attacks (class 2) perform exceptionally well, with near-perfect recall, precision, and F1-score, indicating accurate classification with minimal confusion. In contrast, class 0 (forced error in response attack) has perfect recall but very low precision (0.13), suggesting that many instances of other classes are incorrectly labeled as class 0. This imbalance highlights the need to reduce false positives in this class.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
0	268	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	0	210824	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	195790	1096	0	0	0
3	0	0	1773	5783	0	0	0
4	0	0	201	0	0	0	0
5	1745	811	0	0	0	1483	0
6	0	0	0	659	0	0	1715

Fig. 13. Confusion matrix analysis of Electra Modbus dataset for Method 1.

Table 10

Class-wise metrics for Method 1.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Recall	1,00	1,00	0,99	0,77	0,00	0,37	0,72
Precision	0,13	1,00	0,99	0,77	0,00	1,00	1,00
F1-score	0,23	1,00	0,99	0,77	0,00	0,54	0,84
FNR	0,00	0,00	0,01	0,23	1,00	0,63	0,28

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
0	0	2	0	0	0	288	0
1	0	0	0	0	0	7728	0
2	0	0	7715	0	0	85	0
3	2	17	165	71	5086	2214	0
4	0	0	0	0	243	2	0
5	4	36	0	0	0	4081	0
6	0	0	32	0	609	0	1714

Fig. 14. Confusion matrix analysis of Electra Modbus dataset for Method 1 (with semibalanced data).

Table 11

Class-wise metrics for Method 1 (with semibalanced data).

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Recall	0,00	0,00	0,99	0,01	0,99	0,99	0,73
Precision	0,00	0,00	0,98	1,00	0,04	0,28	1,00
F1-score	0,00	0,00	0,98	0,02	0,08	0,44	0,84
FNR	1,00	1,00	0,01	0,98	0,01	0,01	0,27

Classes 3 (function codes recognition), 5 (response modification), and 6 (write data) show moderate performance. Recall ranges from 0.37 to 0.77, indicating that the model captures a significant portion of the samples but misses some. Classes 5 and 6 have high precision (1.00), indicating correct predictions when made. Class 5, despite its high precision, has low recall (0.37), leading to a high false negative rate (0.63). This suggests that the model should improve detection for this class. In summary, the model should focus on improving class 4 (replay valid packets), adjusting class 0's precision to reduce false positives, and enhancing sensitivity for class 5.

To address this issue, we trained the CNN with a more balanced dataset, ensuring that both *Normal* and *Read Data Attack* instances match the number of data points in the next most represented attack, *Function Codes Recognition Attack*. The precision achieved in this case is 0.4594, and the resulting confusion matrix is depicted in Fig. 14. Hence, to improve performance in detecting and classifying attacks, a larger data set with balanced representations of different attack types is essential. To address this issue, we utilize the GAN method.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
0	29521	0	0	76	0	224	0
1	0	29605	0	1	0	0	0
2	60	242	28989	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	36984	20	13	289
4	105	0	0	567	20829	8059	275
5	700	0	0	1116	4600	27185	118
6	44	0	0	1839	122	35	29873

Fig. 15. Confusion matrix analysis of Electra Modbus dataset for Method 2.

Table 11 presents the results by category for this method (with semibalanced data). Classes 0 and 1 are entirely unrecognized, highlighting a significant issue with the model's ability to classify these classes, as it fails to identify any examples of them. Class 2 performs the best, with almost perfect recall and precision, suggesting that the model consistently classifies it correctly. Class 3 is nearly completely ignored, with a recall of just 0.01, showing that the model is not detecting almost any examples of this class. Classes 4 and 5 exhibit high recall but low precision, indicating that the model tends to over-predict these classes, misclassifying samples from other classes as belonging to them, leading to a higher number of false positives. Class 6 performs quite well, with perfect precision and decent recall, showing that the model is accurate and reasonably sensitive to identify stances of this class. Overall, the model is biased toward certain classes, particularly classes 2, 4, and 5. This suggests the need for better balance in the training data or adjustments to the decision threshold to achieve more equitable performance across all classes.

6.3. Method 2: Improving class balance in attack categories using GANs

The goal of this approach is to ensure that each attack is equally represented. This is accomplished by increasing the data of the attacks to the size of the largest attack (referred to as *Read data Attack*) and discarding some of the normal data until it reaches the same size (785,961 instances) as each attack. Thus, the augmentation of data for underrepresented categories is performed using the GAN described in Section 5.4.

After training and testing the CNN with the balanced dataset generated through GAN, the resulting confusion matrix is depicted in Fig. 15. In this instance, the accuracy achieved was 0.9165. As anticipated, the diagonal elements exhibit the highest values, affirming the overall satisfactory outcome. However, it is evident that certain data points are misclassified by the CNN, particularly within rows 4 (Replay valid packets Attack, the least represented attack) and 5 (Response modification Attack). Consequently, Transfer Learning (TL) is applied to enhance accuracy.

Table 12 complements the previous statements by presenting the results of the metrics applied to each category. Classes 1 and 2 demonstrate the best performance, achieving nearly perfect F1-scores. Similarly, classes 0, 3, and 6 also show excellent results, with high F1-scores and very few errors. In contrast, classes 4 and 5 exhibit the lowest performance, particularly class 4, which has a recall of just 0.70 and an FNR of 0.30. This suggests that many instances of class 4 are not being correctly identified. Overall, while the model performs well, there is room for improvement in classes 4 and 5, especially in terms of recall, to reduce the number of false negatives.

6.4. Method 3: Balancing classes across attack categories using GAN and detecting new attacks with TL

Fig. 16 provides a visual representation of the CNN-TL framework. We begin by utilizing a pretrained model, which in our case is the

Fig. 16. CNN-TL framework.

Table 12
Class-wise metrics for Method 2.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Recall	0,99	1,00	0,99	0,99	0,70	0,81	0,94
Precision	0,97	0,99	1,00	0,91	0,81	0,77	0,98
F1-score	0,98	1,00	0,99	0,95	0,75	0,79	0,96
FNR	0,01	3E-05	0,01	0,01	0,30	0,19	0,06

model obtained in Method 2 (see Section 6.3), referred to as the *CNN-Base (Training and Test)* process, as shown in Fig. 16. Next, we adapt this pretrained model to the new dataset (Electra S7Comm) through the *CNN-TL* procedure. In the early stages of the TL process, the pretrained model's layers are frozen, preserving the knowledge from the Electra Modbus dataset. Once the model is adapted, we train it using the target dataset, as shown in the *CNN-TL Training* phase in Fig. 16. During this phase, the frozen layers retain their original weights, allowing the model to adapt to the new dataset while leveraging prior knowledge from Electra Modbus.

The preprocessing applied to the Electra S7Comm dataset mirrors that of the Electra Modbus dataset, as detailed in Section 5.2. Table 5 shows that the Electra S7Comm dataset has fewer samples than the Electra Modbus dataset and does not include the same types of attacks. To balance the data, all attacks needed to be represented equitably. This was achieved by increasing the samples of the least represented attacks (in this case, the Response modification attack) and discarding samples from the normal data until obtaining the same number of samples for each category. In contrast to Method 2, the optimal approach involved augmenting data for each attack until reaching 15% of the number of samples of the most represented attack, identified as Write Data attack with 2,235,772 samples. This determination was made through an experimental study evaluating the accuracy evolution with augmented data. Therefore, it is recommended that all categories of normal traffic and attacks have 335,365 samples. Similar to Method 2, a GAN architecture (described in Section 5.4) was employed to generate new samples for the Response Modification attack (144,892 samples) and Function codes Recognition attack (265,767 samples) categories, both of which required augmentation. The parameters for the GAN architecture are provided in Table 13.

We analyzed the Electra S7Comm balanced dataset using the CNN-Base model and refined it to produce the modified CNN-TL (Transfer Learning) model. The achieved accuracy is 0.9791, and the corresponding confusion matrix is depicted in Fig. 17.

The confusion matrix diagonal contains the highest values, aligning with expectations and affirming a satisfactory outcome. However, there

Table 13
Parameter optimization for GAN in Electra S7Comm.

Class category	niteration	nsample	nbatch
Response modification	190	140	140 000
Function codes recognition	133	100	200 000

	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	83479	0	0	76	0	241
1	0	83701	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	83802	34	0	0
3	16	0	10	80211	3549	0
4	1	0	0	1270	79898	2569
5	345	0	0	0	2467	81455

Fig. 17. Confusion matrix analysis for the modified pretrained model with the Electra S7Comm dataset.

are instances where the CNN misclassifies data, particularly in rows 3 (Function codes recognition attack), 4 (Response modification attack), and 5 (Write data attack). It is important to note that the Electra S7Comm dataset has the least representation of the first two attacks, while the Write attack is the third least represented attack in the Electra Modbus dataset. These samples were used to train the CNN-Base model. Going forward, we use the pre-trained modified model with the Electra S7Comm dataset to generate the adapted model. The parameters obtained from this training session are preserved and later used in the CNN for the Electra Modbus protocol.

Table 14 complements the previous statements, showing that classes 0, 1, and 2 achieve perfect classification, with recall, precision, and F1-score all at 1.00. Classes 3, 4, and 5 also perform excellently, with recall, precision, and F1-scores above 0.93. The False Negative Rate (FNR) values are low across all classes, indicating very few false negatives. Overall, the model demonstrates near-perfect performance, although minor adjustments could be made to further improve recall in classes 3 and 4.

The pretrained model is integrated into the CNN, with the feature extraction layers frozen. Only the parameters of the classification block are updated during training. The resulting outcome is illustrated by the

Table 14

Class-wise metrics for the modified pretrained model with the Electra S7Comm dataset.

	0	1	2	3	4	5
Recall	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,96	0,95	0,97
Precision	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,98	0,93	0,97
F1-score	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,97	0,94	0,97
FNR	4E-3	0	4E-4	0,04	0,05	0,03

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
0	29843	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	0	29548	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	29198	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	37021	0	0	62
4	0	0	0	0	29501	269	1
5	0	0	0	0	453	33147	0
6	0	0	0	102	0	0	31896

Fig. 18. Confusion matrix analysis of the Electra Modbus dataset after transfer learning with Method 3.

confusion matrix shown in Fig. 18, revealing an impressive accuracy of 0.9960.

This outcome is remarkable as it demonstrates the efficacy of the model in detecting the Replay valid packets attack (row 4), despite its absence during pre-training. In addition, the Normal (row 1) and Read data attack (row 2) classes were accurately detected, which is consistent with their prevalence in the dataset. Interestingly, the Transfer Learning (TL) model shows an improvement in detecting the Forced Error in Response attack (row 0), despite it not being included in the training dataset used for S7comm. This result can be explained by the fact that a Forced Error in Response attack can create conditions that favor other types of attacks, such as response modification or data writing. As a result, the features of the Forced Error in Response attack samples share similarities with those of the mentioned attacks. For example, after triggering an error, attackers could exploit the resulting system failure to inject malicious data or alter the system's responses. It is important to note that both response modification and data writing are represented in the S7comm dataset.

7. Ethical risks and mitigation

The integration of AI into railway systems greatly enhances safety, predictive maintenance, and operational efficiency, allowing for more accurate, proactive, and data-driven management. However, ensuring data privacy and security remains a critical challenge, particularly when handling sensitive passenger information, sensor data, and real-time surveillance feeds.

To address these concerns, this section delves into several key aspects related to ethical and privacy issues in the use of data augmentation and machine learning techniques. It offers a comprehensive discussion of the potential ethical and privacy implications within the specific context of railway scenarios, ensuring the responsible and transparent application of these technologies. This approach not only strengthens the credibility of the research but also ensures its ethical responsibility. The following key points are discussed in detail.

- **Ethical Use of Data:** Regarding the ethical use of data, it can be stated that the origin of the data used is public and auditable, ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union. Since the data does not contain sensitive information, explicit consent has not been required for

its use. Additionally, all the information used has been properly anonymized, ensuring the protection of individuals' privacy and complying with the relevant ethical and legal standards.

- **Data Privacy Risks:** The newly generated samples for the underrepresented classes ensure that the new information remains private, as they have been constructed from publicly available datasets where anonymization and data privacy were strictly ensured. The process of data augmentation leverages these public sources, which have already undergone thorough anonymization procedures, ensuring that no personally identifiable information is included in the generated data. This approach helps maintain the integrity of privacy protection while addressing class imbalance, making the augmented data suitable for training without compromising privacy or violating ethical standards.
- **Fairness and Bias Mitigation:** The data augmentation process involves techniques such as oversampling minority classes (e.g., specific types of attacks or operational failures). However, this approach carries the risk of overrepresenting these classes, which could potentially skew the model's predictions. To mitigate this, the adjustment of GAN parameters to ensure the model does not produce overfitted or biased results is discussed in Section 6.3.
- **Ethical AI Framework:** Finally, in the context of railway scenarios using CNNs and TL, it is crucial to adhere to ethical AI principles to maintain the integrity and reliability of the system, while also building trust among users and stakeholders. As detailed in Sections 5.4 and 6.4, this study offers a comprehensive explanation of the model training process, including the datasets used in each case and the sample augmentation technique employed to address underrepresented classes. Additionally, transfer learning has been applied using a pretrained model. The transparency in the framework's development ensures that both users and stakeholders fully understand the methodology, enabling them to make informed decisions and take appropriate actions based on the model's outcomes. This commitment to transparency and clarity fosters trust, accountability, and responsible use of the models.

8. Practical recommendations for key stakeholders

In order to enhance the practical applicability of our research, we present a series of tailored, actionable recommendations for key stakeholders within the railway cybersecurity ecosystem. These guidelines aim to bridge the gap between academic findings and real-world implementation, empowering stakeholders to leverage machine learning techniques to safeguard critical railway infrastructure. The recommendations are organized according to the specific roles of railway operators, cybersecurity professionals, and policymakers, ensuring each group receives actionable insights relevant to their area of responsibility.

8.1. For railway operators

To enhance both operational efficiency and cybersecurity in railway systems, we propose a set of concrete, interconnected recommendations. First, the deployment of machine learning-based anomaly detection systems across critical network traffic and control layers is essential. This proactive approach enables real-time threat identification and mitigation, reducing response times and minimizing operational disruptions. Complementing this, operational staff should be trained to understand and act on insights generated by these models, ensuring that AI-driven intelligence can be effectively integrated into existing security protocols and strengthening the organization's defensive capabilities.

Equally important is the continuous updating of training datasets to maintain model accuracy and adapt to emerging threats. As attack

patterns evolve, regularly refreshing data ensures machine learning systems remain effective in detecting new vulnerabilities.

In parallel with these AI-focused measures, railway operators must establish robust baseline security controls for operational technologies. This includes implementing network segmentation (security zoning) to isolate critical systems, using secure remote access tools, and separating passenger information systems from core control infrastructure to reduce the overall attack surface.

Cyber preparedness must also be prioritized. Developing incident response plans tailored specifically to the railway sector, and conducting coordinated simulations with national CERTs and transport security agencies, will ensure stakeholders are ready to respond effectively to cyber incidents.

Finally, maintaining a real-time asset inventory across the digital and cyber-physical layers of the railway network is crucial. This enables rapid identification of vulnerable systems and ensures all components are protected against emerging threats, reinforcing the overall cybersecurity posture.

8.2. For cybersecurity professionals

Cybersecurity professionals play a crucial role in safeguarding both information technology (IT) and operational technology (OT) systems from sophisticated cyber threats. To enhance their effectiveness, a strategic integration of machine learning within a multi-layered cybersecurity framework is recommended. This involves complementing conventional security mechanisms—such as firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and antivirus software—with advanced machine learning models capable of identifying anomalies and emerging threats. Such a layered approach increases the likelihood of early detection and timely mitigation.

Given the dynamic nature of cyber threats, it is imperative to implement continuous validation and retraining mechanisms for machine learning models. Regular updates ensure that these systems remain responsive to evolving attack vectors and maintain high levels of accuracy. Furthermore, collaboration with domain-specific experts, including railway engineers, IT professionals, and cybersecurity specialists, is essential. This interdisciplinary approach ensures that machine learning solutions are context-aware and aligned with the unique operational requirements of the railway sector.

To operationalize these strategies effectively, cybersecurity practitioners should adopt recognized threat modeling frameworks such as STRIDE and MITRE ATT&CK for ICS, alongside taxonomies tailored to the railway domain. These tools provide structured methodologies for identifying system vulnerabilities and potential attack paths. Additionally, passive network monitoring tools, such as Zeek and Suricata, adapted to the constraints of low-latency OT environments, offer efficient means of detecting anomalous traffic patterns with minimal operational disruption. Attention must also be directed toward the security of SCADA and signaling infrastructure, including the hardening of programmable logic controllers (PLCs), remote terminal units (RTUs), and interlocking systems. Employing secure firmware practices and implementing encrypted communication protocols—such as TLS over TCP/IP—can significantly enhance the integrity and confidentiality of control data. Lastly, a robust patch management policy, supported by controlled testing environments, is essential for ensuring that critical system updates are applied securely and without compromising system availability or introducing new vulnerabilities.

8.3. For policymakers and regulators

Policymakers play an essential role in shaping the future of railway cybersecurity by establishing regulatory frameworks and supporting strategic initiatives. To facilitate systemic improvements, it is crucial for policymakers to encourage the development of industry-specific cybersecurity standards that integrate machine learning technologies. Such frameworks would enhance the protection of critical

railway infrastructure against evolving cyber threats, ensuring that systems remain resilient and adaptable to future challenges. Furthermore, promoting research and development focused on innovative machine learning applications in the transportation sector will drive continuous advancements in cybersecurity technologies, reinforcing the preparedness of railway systems to face emerging risks.

In addition to fostering innovation, policymakers must prioritize collaboration and information sharing among public and private stakeholders. Railway operators, cybersecurity firms, and regulatory bodies should be encouraged to work together to accelerate the adoption of machine learning-based solutions within the railway industry. Facilitating these connections will not only promote the effective integration of new technologies but also enable rapid responses to evolving cyber threats.

Policymakers should also focus on creating targeted regulatory frameworks that enhance cybersecurity across the sector. This includes the development of railway-specific cybersecurity policies based on international standards such as IEC 62443 and ISO/TS 22163, establishing enforceable cybersecurity requirements to ensure a baseline level of protection. Additionally, public-private collaboration should be further supported by frameworks for threat intelligence sharing, funding mechanisms for cybersecurity research, and coordinated joint cybersecurity exercises. These efforts will improve industry-wide preparedness for cyber incidents.

A critical component of railway cybersecurity is securing the supply chain and procurement processes. Policymakers should establish guidelines to vet hardware and software suppliers, mandate the inclusion of cybersecurity clauses in procurement contracts, and implement regular audits of third-party vendors to maintain high security standards. Furthermore, aligning cybersecurity regulations with physical safety standards will establish a more integrated safety-security governance model, enhancing both the safety and security of the railway system.

By adopting these recommendations, stakeholders across the railway cybersecurity ecosystem will be better equipped to leverage machine learning technologies effectively. These strategies will not only mitigate current cyber threats but will also provide the tools necessary to anticipate and address future challenges in an increasingly complex and interconnected digital landscape.

9. Conclusions and future work

This paper explores the application of machine learning techniques for detecting and classifying cyberattacks in railway systems. The primary objective was to assess and compare different detection approaches, highlighting the impact of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for data augmentation and Transfer Learning (TL) with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).

The results underscore the effectiveness of GAN-based augmentation, which significantly improved detection accuracy from 45.94% (without augmentation) to 91.65% by addressing data sparsity and imbalance. Additionally, the integration of TL-based models further enhanced performance, achieving an outstanding 99.60% accuracy in detecting and classifying cyberattacks.

These findings highlight the critical role of advanced machine learning techniques in enhancing cybersecurity for railway infrastructure. To ensure continued adaptability and resilience against evolving threats, future research should prioritize real-time evaluation, assessing both detection accuracy and the system's ability to operate within railway time constraints. Additionally, exploring the cross-domain applicability of these methods—such as their transferability to aviation, maritime, and energy systems—will help determine their effectiveness in diverse environments. Lastly, ensuring seamless integration with existing railway infrastructure while maintaining high security and operational efficiency remains a key focus for further study.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Beatriz Otero Calviño: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Data curation. **Eva Rodríguez:** Supervision, Formal analysis, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Juan José Costa:** Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Validation. **Mercedes Oriol:** Validation, Data curation, Visualization, Formal analysis, Software, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Beatriz Otero reports was provided by Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. Beatriz Otero reports a relationship with Polytechnic University of Catalonia that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The datasets used are in the public domain.

References

- [1] A. Gabriel, F. Brauner, A. Lotter, F. Fiedrich, O.A. Mudimu, Cyber security flaws and deficiencies in the European rail traffic management system towards cyber-attacks, in: Proceeding of the 15th ISCRAM Conference, 2018.
- [2] W. Wang, F. Harrou, B. Bouyeddou, S.-M. Senouci, Y. Sun, Cyber-attacks detection in industrial systems using artificial intelligence-driven methods, *Int. J. Crit. Infrastruct. Prot.* 38 (2022) 100542.
- [3] S. Ali, S.U. Rehman, A. Imran, G. Adeem, Z. Iqbal, K.-I. Kim, Comparative evaluation of AI-based techniques for zero-day attacks detection, *Electron.* 11 (23) (2022) 3934.
- [4] M. Saqlain, Q. Abbas, J.Y. Lee, A deep convolutional neural network for wafer defect identification on an imbalanced dataset in semiconductor manufacturing processes, *IEEE Trans. Semicond. Manuf.* 33 (3) (2020) 436–444.
- [5] H.A. Al-Najjar, B. Pradhan, R. Sarkar, G. Beydoun, A. Alamri, A new integrated approach for landslide data balancing and spatial prediction based on generative adversarial networks (GAN), *Remote. Sens.* 13 (19) (2021) 4011.
- [6] T.V. Khoa, D.T. Hoang, N.L. Trung, C.T. Nguyen, T.T.T. Quynh, D.N. Nguyen, N.V. Ha, E. Dutkiewicz, Deep transfer learning: A novel collaborative learning model for cyberattack detection systems in IoT networks, *IEEE Internet Things J.* (2022).
- [7] J. Zhao, S. Shetty, J.W. Pan, C. Kamhoua, K. Kwiat, Transfer learning for detecting unknown network attacks, *EURASIP J. Inf. Secur.* 2019 (2019) 1–13.
- [8] L. Yang, A. Shami, A transfer learning and optimized CNN based intrusion detection system for internet of vehicles, in: ICC 2022-IEEE International Conference on Communications, IEEE, 2022, pp. 2774–2779.
- [9] Á.L. Perales Gómez, L. Fernández Maimó, A. Huertas Celdrán, F.J. García Clemente, C. Cadenas Sarmiento, C.J. Del Canto Masa, R. Méndez Nistal, On the generation of anomaly detection datasets in industrial control systems, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 177460–177473, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2958284>.
- [10] B. Ning, S. Qiu, T. Zhao, Y. Li, Power IoT attack samples generation and detection using generative adversarial networks, in: 2020 IEEE 4th Conference on Energy Internet and Energy System Integration, EI2, IEEE, 2020, pp. 3721–3724.
- [11] Á.L. Perales Gómez, L. Fernández Maimó, A. Huertas Celdrán, F.J. García Clemente, M. Gil Pérez, G. Martínez Pérez, SafeMan: A unified framework to manage cybersecurity and safety in manufacturing industry, *Softw.: Pr. Exp.* 51 (3) (2021) 607–627, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/spe.2879>, URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/spe.2879>. arXiv:<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/spe.2879>.
- [12] Y. Li, X. Ji, C. Li, X. Xu, W. Yan, X. Yan, Y. Chen, W. Xu, Cross-domain anomaly detection for power industrial control system, in: 2020 IEEE 10th International Conference on Electronics Information and Emergency Communication, ICEIEC, IEEE, 2020, pp. 383–386.
- [13] M. Conti, D. Donadel, F. Turrin, A survey on industrial control system testbeds and datasets for security research, *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutor.* 23 (4) (2021) 2248–2294.
- [14] J.-R. Jiang, Y.-T. Lin, Deep learning anomaly classification using multi-attention residual blocks for industrial control systems, *Sens.* 22 (23) (2022) 9084.
- [15] J.-R. Jiang, Y.-T. Chen, Industrial control system anomaly detection and classification based on network traffic, *IEEE Access* 10 (2022) 41874–41888.
- [16] V. Vasilyev, A. Vulfin, A. Kirillova, Algorithms for proactive security of industrial systems based on machine learning technologies, in: Information Technology and Nanotechnology, ITNT-2022, 2022.
- [17] T. Berghout, M. Benbouzid, EL-NAHL: Exploring labels autoencoding in augmented hidden layers of feedforward neural networks for cybersecurity in smart grids, *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.* 226 (2022) 108680, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2022.108680>, URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0951832022003131>.
- [18] M. Ramprasath, M.V. Anand, S. Hariharan, Image classification using convolutional neural networks, *Int. J. Pure Appl. Math.* 119 (17) (2018) 1307–1319.
- [19] A. Pandey, D. Wang, A new framework for CNN-based speech enhancement in the time domain, *IEEE/ACM Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.* 27 (7) (2019) 1179–1188.
- [20] P. Li, J. Li, G. Wang, Application of convolutional neural network in natural language processing, in: 2018 15th International Computer Conference on Wavelet Active Media Technology and Information Processing, ICCWAMTIP, IEEE, 2018, pp. 120–122.
- [21] J. Kim, J. Kim, H. Kim, M. Shim, E. Choi, CNN-based network intrusion detection against denial-of-service attacks, *Electron.* 9 (6) (2020) 916.
- [22] Z. Okonkwo, E. Foo, Q. Li, Z. Hou, A CNN based encrypted network traffic classifier, in: Australasian Computer Science Week 2022, 2022, pp. 74–83.
- [23] L. Mohammadpour, T.C. Ling, C.S. Liew, A. Aryanfar, A survey of CNN-based network intrusion detection, *Appl. Sci.* 12 (16) (2022) 8162.
- [24] A. Creswell, T. White, V. Dumoulin, K. Arulkumaran, B. Sengupta, A.A. Bharath, Generative adversarial networks: An overview, *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* 35 (1) (2018) 53–65.
- [25] F. Zhuang, Z. Qi, K. Duan, D. Xi, Y. Zhu, H. Zhu, H. Xiong, Q. He, A comprehensive survey on transfer learning, *Proc. IEEE* 109 (1) (2020) 43–76.
- [26] G. Vrbancič, V. Podgorelec, Transfer learning with adaptive fine-tuning, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 196197–196211.
- [27] Q. Abu Al-Hajja, S. Zein-Sabatto, An efficient deep-learning-based detection and classification system for cyber-attacks in IoT communication networks, *Electron.* 9 (12) (2020) 2152.
- [28] S. McElwee, Probabilistic Clustering Ensemble Evaluation for Intrusion Detection (Ph.D. thesis), 2018, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13702.83525>.
- [29] K. Fysarakis, et al., Phoenix—a European cyber resilience framework with artificial-intelligence-assisted orchestration, automation & response capabilities for business continuity and recovery, incident response, and information exchange, in: 2023 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience, CSR, IEEE, 2023, pp. 538–545.
- [30] Electra dataset, 2023, <http://perception.inf.um.es/ICS-datasets/>. (Accessed March 2025).
- [31] B. Dutertre, Formal modeling and analysis of the modbus protocol, in: Critical Infrastructure Protection 1, Springer, 2008, pp. 189–204.
- [32] E. Rodríguez, P. Valls, B. Otero, J.J. Costa, J. Verdú, M.A. Pajuelo, R. Canal, Transfer-learning-based intrusion detection framework in IoT networks, *Sens.* 22 (15) (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/s22155621>, URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/22/15/5621>.
- [33] M. Abadi, A. Agarwal, P. Barham, E. Brevdo, Z. Chen, C. Citro, G.S. Corrado, A. Davis, J. Dean, M. Devin, S. Ghemawat, I. Goodfellow, A. Harp, G. Irving, M. Isard, Y. Jia, R. Jozefowicz, L. Kaiser, M. Kudlur, J. Levenberg, D. Mane, R. Monga, S. Moore, D. Murray, C. Olah, M. Schuster, J. Shlens, B. Steiner, I. Sutskever, K. Talwar, P. Tucker, V. Vanhoucke, V. Vasudevan, F. Viegas, O. Vinyals, P. Warden, M. Wattenberg, M. Wicke, Y. Yu, X. Zheng, TensorFlow: Large-scale machine learning on heterogeneous distributed systems, 2016, URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1603.04467>. arXiv:1603.04467.

- [34] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, et al., Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 12 (2011) 2825–2830.
- [35] W. McKinney, et al., Data structures for statistical computing in Python, in: *SciPy*, Vol. 445, 2010, pp. 51–56.
- [36] C.R. Harris, K.J. Millman, S.J. van der Walt, et al., Array programming with NumPy, *Nat.* 585 (2020) 357–362, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2>.
- [37] J. Lee, K. Park, GAN-based imbalanced data intrusion detection system, *Pers. Ubiquitous Comput.* 25 (2021) 121–128.